

ADVANCED FOREIGN METHODS OF ENSURING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION

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Abstract. This article discusses the issue of improving the quality of foreign language teaching through the introduction of non-traditional teaching methods in higher education institutions. Quality of education-determines the state and outcome of the educational process in society, as well as the formation and development of professional, domestic and civic competence of the individual in accordance with the needs and requirements of society. The quality of education is assessed by indicators that describe various aspects of the educational activity of the educational institution. These indicators include the content of education, forms and methods of teaching, material and technical base, staffing, etc., which ensure the development of students' competencies.

Keywords: language teaching, CLT, computer assisted language learning, modern approaches.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается вопрос повышения качества преподавания иностранного языка за счет внедрения нетрадиционных методов обучения в высших учебных заведениях. Качество образования - определяет состояние и результаты образовательного процесса в обществе, а также формирование и развитие профессиональной, бытовой и гражданской компетентности личности в соответствии с потребностями и требованиями общества. Качество образования оценивается показателями, характеризующими различные стороны образовательной деятельности образовательного учреждения. К этим показателям относятся содержание образования, формы и методы обучения, материально-техническая база, кадровое обеспечение и т.д., обеспечивающие развитие компетенций обучающихся.

Ключевые слова: обучение языку, CLT, компьютерное обучение языку, современные подходы.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalarida o'qitishning noan'anaviy usullarini joriy etish orqali chet tillarini o'qitish sifatini oshirish masalasi muhokama qilinadi. Ta'lim sifati - jamiyatdagi ta'lim jarayonining holati va natijalarini, shuningdek, jamiyat ehtiyojlari va talablariga muvofiq shaxsning kasbiy, maishiy va fuqarolik kompetentsiyasini shakllantirish va rivojlantirishni belgilaydi. Ta'lim sifati ta'lim muassasasi ta'lim faoliyatining turli tomonlarini tavsiflovchi ko'rsatkichlar bilan baholanadi. Bu ko'rsatkichlar o'quvchilarning kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishni ta'minlovchi ta'lim mazmuni, o'qitishning shakl va usullari, moddiy-texnik bazasi, kadrlar bilan ta'minlanganligi va boshqalarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Til o'qitish, CLT, kompyuter yordamida til o'rganish, zamonaviy yondashuvlar.

Introduction:

The last century has witnessed a major focus on language teaching as an overall professional section in the education sector. However, the concept "method" was the bottleneck, and the main focus of this concept and consequently got the most attention. This concept represents the practice of teaching as a research-based and systematic set of teaching practices. In a simple definition, you can call it the way of linking theory with practice. Methods are the teaching systems which is usually fixed with the necessary techniques and practices. The 1950s to the 1980s is the

age of methods The two main schools that discussed language teaching methodologies are Situational Language Teaching and Audio-Lingualism. Other methods, which are emerged in between the before-mentioned schools, like the Silent Way, Suggestopedia, Community Language Learning, and Total Physical Response. After that, some other methods came to the education field in a more salient way. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) was closer to the term approach rather than methods and considered one of the methods used innovation. Other methods have concurrent at the same time of CLT emergence, like the Natural Approach, Cooperative Language Learning, Content-Based Teaching, and Task-Based Teaching. (Rogers, 2001). It was noticed, that the ability to communicate effectively in a foreign language has become a fundamental goal of many language programs across the world. The communicative language teaching (CLT), with its emphasis on ‘what it means to know a language and to be able to put that knowledge to use in communicating with people in a variety of settings and situations’ (Hedge 2000: 45), has become increasingly central to school modern foreign language (MFL) programs, at least in Western contexts, since it first emerged in the early 1970s. (East, 2019). The word “innovation” is often used to describe a product or development that is “new” or “enhanced” in some way but only when successfully implemented. According to (De Lano et al., 1994) innovation includes four key terms: 1- Change 2- Development 3- Novelty 4- Improvement. In my paper, I will try to explain how the traditional methods were and how the before-mentioned four key terms have participated in moving from traditional to innovative.

Methodology: The traditional teaching methods were depending on a systematic behavioral analysis of learners’ pragmatic language learning needs. According to (Nurutdinova et al., 2016) most of the teaching conduct in a sophisticated manner that focuses on the teacher as the center of the class. Charles Curran (1972) was one of the main researchers who developed the first traditional methods or what was called the community-based/advisor method. In his theory learner was highly dependant on experts who expected to play the major role of advising and guiding. Suggestopedia is also another traditional method developed by Georgi Lozanov in 1978. The method was depending on memorizing more and more while moving forward in the course where the authority of the teacher still salient. (ibid). The need for alternative methods to be used in language teaching was one of the main push factors to move from traditional approaches to innovative ones. However, as we have discussed earlier there is no possibility to neglect the traditional tactics and pretend to create something from scratch. There is a need to adapt to the new models and do an integration. (Nurutdinova et al., 2016). While speaking about inductive and productive practices, it has been always argued that inductive methods increase the consolidation of a subject and would help in evaluating the performance. The Silent Way method was developed by K.Gatteno. He tried to focus more on students and that was one of the courageous steps towards innovation. He concluded that students should speak more while the teacher should speak less. Computer-assisted language learning, this technique has not started from the beginning innovatively as many people think. The computer-based program which was established in the 1960s and intended to be used for language teaching focused on the grammatical and lexical side of language teaching. However, the development has started since that time to improve this technique and the usage of artificial intelligence which started to pave the way in front of making the learning more interactive. The task-based methods were also one of the transitional methods that started to bring innovative ideas to the teaching methodology. The communicative part of this approach is closer to the communicative approach than to the traditional one and will speak about it in detail.

Analysis: One of the main approaches that adapted innovation tactics and techniques was the communicative language teaching approach (CLT). The CLT suggested that we are using language to express meaning and that means that interaction and communication are the primary functions of language. Grammar and structure are for sure important and language cannot be learned without basic knowledge of them, but the functional and communicative meaning is also very important. The before mentioned aspects should complement each other to achieve the goal of teaching. The innovative pioneers suggest that the ultimate goal for them in teaching a foreign language is building communicative competence. They tried to create a simulation inside classrooms to make students feel like in real life (Liao, 2000). It is also noticed that the use of new technologies would allow smooth and swift facilitation of curricula that are highly dependent on communication and simulation. (Nurutdinova et al., 2016). Another interesting suggestion by (Bonwell & Eison, 1991) have assumed that there are several techniques that can support and promote active learning:

- The visual media usage during the lessons (video, photos, PowerPoint).
- Training students to take notes during classes.
- The use of smartphones or computers during lectures or through the time of teaching.
- Empowering students to solve problems during a case study assignment.
- The use of simulation, and drilling.
- Development of collaborative learning approaches.

Results:

Some researchers give examples of activities from a different point of view, they proposed that the more accessibility provided for teacher education the more they will be able to do analyzing the classroom practice. That will support teachers seeking to establish a more communicative classroom environment. For teachers who are adapting the traditional approach and are more controlled and tied to the form-oriented activities, while the teachers on the opposite side will establish dimensions for innovation and expansion. In this way, they can grow but retain a sense of security and value in what they have done before. (LIDDICOAT et al., 2011)

The innovation could be achieved also by making learning opportunities available for everyone. That could be done through the facilitation of enhancing interaction and minimize perceptual mismatches between what is intended and what is understood. The integration of language skills could be also one of the main improvements of the teaching strategy. As we saw before, that traditional approaches were trying to keep the authority of the tutor to the highest level while the innovative approach promotes learner autonomy, raise cultural consciousness, and ensure social relevance.

Challenges of applying the innovative approach:

It was assumed that teacher capacity to teach through communicative and innovative way would be challenging due to the lack of expertise in this field. Most of the teachers are not native speakers and do not have enough proficiency to communicate fluently with students. In many cases teacher they were not aware of new innovative methods. It was noticed also that traditions sometimes play some role in this regard. One of the main challenges was that the main exams for admissions and also getting some job was more traditional oriented. (Liao, 2000)

Conclusion:

Whether we are going to use the traditional or innovative methods we have to make sure that teaching goals should be established according to the needs, lacks, and necessities of the targeted student population and educational environment to strengthen motivations and ensure

interactive participation in the learning process. (Nurutdinova et al., 2016). Research has revealed that, when teachers encounter the day-to-day realities of work with real students in real classrooms, they interpret and implement the methodology in a variety of ways that may often include more traditional and ‘teacher-fronted’ elements. Andon and Eckerth (2009), for example, found not only that teachers’ beliefs and choices were influenced by requirements to respond to what was happening in their classrooms on a lesson-by-lesson basis, but also that a range of conflicting beliefs held by the teachers could exert an influence on pedagogical decisions. They conclude that teachers practiced ‘principled eclecticism’ and assert that this was ‘entirely appropriate’. (East, 2019). In most of the schools, there are tens of thousands of foreign language teachers and their supervisors who are awake or will soon be awake, to the job we face. Most of them are frightened, or at best very diffident because they know better than anyone else how ill-equipped they are to do what is expected of them, and how long it takes to become properly equipped in the foreign language skills they need. (Dostert et al., 1960)

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